

Flavonoids from *Medicago polymorpha* Roxb.

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In a previous communications^{1,2}, we reported the occurrence of a new sterol, two rare amides, aurantiamide acetate and auranamide and a 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxyflavone (1a) in the whole plant of *Medicago polymorpha* Roxb. (Fam.: Leguminosae). We now report the isolation and characterisation of three more 5-hydroxyflavone derivatives from the benzene extract of this plant.

The benzene extract of the defatted whole plant of *M. polymorpha* on chromatography over silica gel afforded a yellow crystalline solid from the benzene eluates, m.p. 222–24°, C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (M⁺ 314); λ_{max} (EtOH) 242, 248, 254, 260 and 337 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3330 and 1620 cm⁻¹; gave positive Shinoda test. It was characterised as 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone (1b) on the basis of its spectral analysis³.

The benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1) eluates obtained from the same chromatogram afforded successively two compounds, MP-2 and MP-3.

- 1a; R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = H
 1b; R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃, R₃ = OH
 1c; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = H, R₃ = OH
 1d; R₁ = R₂ = OH, R₃ = H

The compound MP-2, m.p. 285–86°, C₁₆H₁₂O₆ (M⁺ 284); λ_{max} (EtOH) 262 and 358 nm, gave positive Shinoda test. Its uv, ir, pmr and particularly the mass spectral data compared fairly well with those reported⁴ for 5,4'-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavone (1c). The compound MP-3, m.p. 327–29°, C₁₅H₁₀O₆ (M⁺ 270) gave positive Shinoda test. It was identified as apigenin (1d) by its spectral analysis and comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc, co-ir and pmr spectral data) with an authentic sample.

Although the genus *Medicago* is a rich source of isoflavonoid class of compounds⁵, the occurrence of 5-hydroxyflavone derivatives in this species is being reported for the first time.

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Extractives of *Sequoiadendron giganteum*

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OUR interest in the isolation of natural products having potential anticancer activity, led us to reinvestigate the leaves of *S. giganteum* which belongs to the family Taxidiaceae, a rich source of lignans of podophylloxin type. Podophylloxin is an active anticancer agent^{1,2}. Previous work on this plant resulted in the isolation of biflavonoids³ and sequirenes (norlignans)⁴. Material used in the present investigation was collected from the higher region of Kashmir and identified at Botany Department, University of Kashmir, Srinagar. Air-dried needles (5 kg) were extracted with petroleum ether and the concentrated extract was chromatographed on a column of silica gel to yield 1, m.p. 145–46° (eluted with benzene) and 2, m.p. 153–55° (with benzene-ethyl acetate, 9:1). The defatted plant material was then extracted exhaustively with ethanol which was concentrated and chromatographed on a column of silica gel. Benzene-ethyl acetate (4:1) eluate gave 3 which was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 310°.

Savinin (1) had λ_{max} (MeOH) 237, 293 and 334 nm and ν_{max} 1735, 1640 and 1600 cm⁻¹. Pmr spectrum of 1 showed two 2H singlets at δ 5.95 and 6.00 attributable to methylenedioxy functions. AB part of an ABX system was discernible at δ 2.8, all eight lines being well-resolved (J_{AB} 17 Hz, J_{AX} 10 Hz and J_{BX} 4 Hz) and the X part as a broad multiplet at δ 3.75. A 2H doublet appeared further downfield at δ 4.28 (J 5 Hz). It was identified on the basis of m.p. 145–46° (lit.⁵ 146°) and spectral data as savinin. Stigmast-22-enol was identified on the basis of physical⁶ and spectral data (ir, pmr and mass). 3 gave a positive test with FeCl₃. It formed acetyl and methyl ether derivatives whose pmr analysis followed by a direct comparison of 3